

ISic3592

I.Sicily inscription 3592

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

stone

Object

sima

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Leontini

Place of origin (modern)

Lentini

Provenance

excavation of a sanctuary with monumental altar in contrada Scala
Portazza, on east side of the modern town (map Frasca (2005)

138 fig.1

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lentini

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645671

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 60.1012

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 59.1106

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 55.1012bis

Frasca, M. 2005. Hera a Leontini. In Gigli, R.(eds.), *MEGALA NESOI. Studi dedicati a Giovanni Rizza per il suo ottantesimo compleanno*. Catania. pp. 137-145. At 143 fig.6

Frasca, M. 2009. Leontini. *Archeologia di una colonia greca*. Rome. At 118 no.7

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